

Partners

ACTA – The Agricultural Technical Institutes
 Agrosolutions – InVivo
 AIDER – Integrated Sustainable Economic Reliable Agriculture
 APCA – French Chambers of Agriculture
 ASR – Rural Development Association
 BA – Baertschi Agrartecnic AG
 BZ – Barwy Zdrowia
 BioForum – BioForum Vlaanderen
 Bionext
 CRA-W – Walloon Agricultural Research Centre
 CREA – Council for Agricultural Research and Economics
 ERF – Exploitation Public Reserved Lands Flevoland
 ESA – Higher School in Education and Research in Agriculture
 FiBL – Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
 FIRAB – Italian Foundation for Research in Organic and Biodynamic Agriculture
 HS – The Rural Economy and Agricultural Society in Scania
 INAGRO – Research and Advice in Agriculture and Horticulture
 INRA – French National Institute for Agricultural Research
 IT – INRA Transfert S.A.
 IUNG-PIB – Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation, State Research Institute
 LEAF – Linking Environment And Farming
 LWK – Chamber of Agriculture Lower Saxony
 MZ – Mühle Rytz AG
 NSF – NSF Romania

FR
 FR
 RO
 FR
 IT
 CH
 PL
 BE
 NL
 BE
 IT
 NL
 FR
 CH

Map of DiverIMPACTS partners

IT	ÖMKi – Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture	HU
SE	ORC – Organic Research Centre	UK
	SOCOPRO – Agriculture producers' service centre	BE
BE	SLU – Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	SE
FR	TI – Thünen Institute for Biodiversity	DE
FR	UCL – Catholic University of Louvain	BE
	UvA – University of Amsterdam	NL
PL	WUR – FSE – Wageningen University & Research,	
UK	Farming Systems Ecology Group	NL
DE	WUR-PAGV – Wageningen University & Research,	
CH	Applied Arable and Vegetable Research	NL
RO	Wal.Agri SA	BE

Contact

Project coordinator:

Dr. Antoine Messéan, INRA, France
 E-Mail: antoine.messean@inra.fr

DiverIMPACTS facts

Funding: Horizon 2020, European Union and Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)

- > Call: Rural Renaissance – Fostering innovation and business opportunities
- > Topic: RUR-06-2016 (Scope A – Annual crops): Crop diversification systems for the delivery of food, feed, industrial products and ecosystems services – from farm benefits to value-chain organisation
- > Grant agreement No 727482
- > Project duration: 5 years (June 2017 to May 2022)
- > Number of partners: 34 from 11 European countries
- > Project Deputy: Didier Stilmant, CRA-W, BE

Imprint

Text: Dr. Antoine Messéan, INRA; Malgorzata Conder, FiBL
 Layout: Simone Bissig, FiBL

Photo credits

Hansueli Dierauer (FiBL): p. 1 (1), Ilka Richter: p. 2 (1), p. 3 (2); Barbara Früh (FiBL), p. 2 (2); Cornelia Kupferschmid: p. 2 (3); Matthias Klais (FiBL) p. 2 (4); Guy Akkermans: p. 3 (1)

The views expressed on this flyer are the sole responsibility of the authors and publishers and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on behalf of the Commission is responsible for the use which might be made of the information contained herein.
 DiverIMPACTS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 727482 (DiverIMPACTS) and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI.

www.diverimpacts.net
 © FiBL / INRA, 2017

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727482 (DiverIMPACTS)

Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research "SERI" State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI

DiverIMPACTS A Horizon 2020 multi-actor project

European arable agricultural systems are often characterised by short rotations or even monocultures, leading to problems such as higher pest pressure, soil erosion, loss of soil fertility, and loss of biodiversity.

In this context, the overall goal of DiverIMPACTS is to promote the diversification of cropping systems, with the aim to improve productivity, help deliver ecosystem services, and support the development of resource-efficient and sustainable value chains.

DiverIMPACTS will develop a range of technical and organisational innovations to help remove barriers all along the value chain from farmers to consumers, as well as create strategies and recommendations to strengthen crop diversification practises on the long-term.

The project has 34 partners from 11 countries and covers the main biogeographical regions in Europe.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727482 (DiverIMPACTS)

www.diverimpacts.net

DiverIMPACTS Key activities

- DiverIMPACTS co-designs technical and organisational innovations to promote crop diversification and co-learning.
Field day in Borwede, Germany.

Photo: Bio Suisse

- DiverIMPACTS demonstrates the benefits of crop diversification for farmers and society.
Market stand, Switzerland.

- DiverIMPACTS aims to remove barriers to crop diversification at the farm, value chain and territory levels.
Field visits with practitioners, Switzerland.

- DiverIMPACTS develops comprehensive and long-term strategies and tools for more resilient crop diversification.
Intercropping with soya and winter oat, Switzerland.

Case studies and field experiments

DiverIMPACTS demonstrates the potential of diversification through 25 multi-actor case studies.

Picture: Field trial of mixed crop with wheat and maize.

DiverIMPACTS aims to quantify the performances of crop diversification using 10 existing field experiments across Europe.

Picture: Long-term field experiment in Borwede, Germany.

Promoting crop diversification in Europe: Expected DiverIMPACTS results and outcomes

- > Assessment of the direct and indirect impacts of crop diversification along the crop value chain;
- > Identification of success and failure factors of crop diversification experiences;
- > Policy analysis and recommendations for tailored policy instruments;
- > A multi-criteria assessment tool designed to assess benefits and drawbacks of crop diversification;
- > Specifications of machinery equipment that could help foster crop diversification;
- > Logistic and contractual schemes as well as economic instruments to promote crop diversification;
- > Novel business models resulting from crop diversification and short supply chains;
- > Innovative collaboration paths between rural actors, from farmers to consumers;
- > A network of key actors and experts of sociotechnical systems beyond the project;
- > A learning-for-innovation platform and new training and education strategy to enhance crop diversification;
- > A long-term network of standardised field experiments across Europe;
- > A practical decision tree to help actors assess benefits of crop diversification.

DiverIMPACTS work packages

1. Identification of success and failure factors of crop diversification
2. Promoting crop diversification in case studies through actor-oriented research
3. Quantification of the benefits from diversified cropping systems through field experiments
4. Sustainability assessment of crop diversification at the farm, value chain and territory levels
5. From lock-ins to innovations and value chain redesign
6. Strategies, methods and tools to sustain crop diversification all along the value chain
7. Transfer, dissemination and communication of the project outcomes
8. Consortium coordination and project management

What is crop diversification?

Crop diversification can be achieved using a variety of techniques, such as

- > Growing different crop species on the same land in successive growing seasons (i.e. rotation);
- > Growing different crop species on the same land within a growing season (i.e. multiple cropping);
- > Growing different species in proximity in the same field (i.e. mixed, row, and strip intercropping).